

1 **Physicochemical structure of a polyacrylic acid stabilized nanoparticle alum**
2 **(nanoalum) adjuvant governs TH1 differentiation of CD4+ T cells**

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5 The growing shift to subunit antigen vaccines underscores the need for adjuvants that can
6 enhance the magnitude and quality of immune response. Aluminum salts or alums are the first
7 adjuvants with a long history of clinical use. Alum predominantly induces T helper 2 (TH2) type
8 immunity in animal models, characterized by antibody production with little to no induction of
9 antigen-specific T cells. The lack of cell-mediated or T helper 1 (TH1) immunity makes alum
10 adjuvants ineffective in mounting durable responses against diseases like tuberculosis,
11 malaria and HIV. Here we show that the clinically approved adjuvant, Alhydrogel, reformulated
12 as a stable nanoparticle (nanoalum) with the anionic polymer polyacrylic acid (PAA) induces
13 structure-dependent TH1 response against the recombinant tuberculosis antigen ID93. We
14 found that PAA adsorption to Alhydrogel was a key parameter affecting nanoalum
15 adjuvanticity. Adsorption depended on various factors, most notably formulation pH, and
16 directly correlated with immunological response in mice, enhancing known hallmarks of a
17 murine TH1 type response: induction of antigen-specific IFN- γ secreting CD4+ T cells and
18 IgG2c subclass of antibodies. Our results demonstrate a correlation between a measurable
19 nanoalum property and immunological response, providing a structural basis to derive a
20 beneficial immunological outcome from a clinically approved adjuvant.

21 **Introduction**

22 Adjuvants are crucial components in modern subunit vaccines that help augment the
23 magnitude, durability, and quality of the adaptive immune response. For over 90 years,
24 aluminum salts including aluminum oxyhydroxide and aluminum phosphate,
25 collectively referred to as “alum”, were the only adjuvants used in human vaccines.

26 However for several vaccine targets including influenza, shingles, HPV and HBV alum
27 alone is not effective in promoting protective immunity. In the last decade several
28 vaccines with novel adjuvants were granted FDA approval ¹⁻⁴, marking a golden age in
29 adjuvant discovery and development. While aluminum salt adjuvants remain a
30 benchmark due to their long clinical history, advances in formulation technology are
31 providing vaccine developers access to an increasing number of adjuvants that induce
32 a more diverse and long-lasting immunological response than alum alone ⁵⁻⁸.

33 Regular aluminum salt formulations – in combinations with pure antigens that do not
34 possess their own immuno-stimulatory activity – induce a predominantly TH2 response
35 in animal models, characterized by secretion of cytokines such as IL-4 and IL-10. These
36 cytokines promote differentiation of B cells to antibody-secreting plasma cells while
37 simultaneously inhibiting TH1 CD4+ T cell responses (characterized by IFN- γ and TNF
38 production) and cytotoxic CD8 T cell functions crucial for antibody maturation and
39 protection against infectious diseases such as tuberculosis, pertussis, malaria and HIV.
40 Combining pathogen-associated molecular pattern (PAMP) molecules such as toll-lik
41 receptor (TLR) ligands with alum can induce a more balanced immune response,
42 usually elevating the TH1 responses ^{9, 10}.

43 Structurally, aluminum salt adjuvants are highly heterogeneous and consist of
44 nanometer sized particles that form aggregates ranging from a few micrometers to
45 hundreds of micrometers in size. Previous studies using bottom-up synthesis
46 approaches such as co-precipitation of aluminum salts with stabilizers have shown that
47 nanoparticles of various aluminum oxide phases in the 100-400 nm scale can augment
48 adjuvant activity without the need for additional PAMPs ¹¹⁻¹³. For instance, Li et al
49 showed that nanoparticles of aluminum hydroxide produce a stronger adjuvant activity
50 compared to micron sized particles¹⁴, potentially due to greater cellular uptake and
51 inflammasome activation by nanoparticles relative to the micron-sized particles¹⁵. We
52 recently introduced a scalable high pressure microfluidization process to reduce

53 particle size of the clinically approved aluminum oxyhydroxide (AlO(OH)) adjuvant
54 Alhydrogel¹⁶. The high shear forces exerted during the top-down microfluidization
55 process breaks the micron-sized Alhydrogel aggregates, and the addition of a low
56 molecular weight polyacrylic acid (PAA) – an anionic polyelectrolyte – prevents re-
57 aggregation and provides exceptional long-term colloidal stability. The PAA-stabilized
58 sub-100 nm version of Alhydrogel, “nanoalum”, induced TH1 differentiation of CD4+ T
59 cells, indicated by the antigen-specific secretion of interferon-gamma (IFN- γ) and tumor
60 necrosis factor (TNF) cytokines. Furthermore, the nanoalum adjuvant performed
61 equivalent to a potent TLR4 adjuvant known to induce a robust TH1 immune response
62 and was also effective in promoting protective immunity against a lethal influenza
63 challenge. The prospect of an alum-based TH1 inducing adjuvant – without additional
64 PAMP molecules – is attractive as it builds on the impressive safety record of standard
65 alum and thus warrants further characterization and development.

66 Interestingly, we found that TH1 induction was unique to PAA-stabilized nanoalum,
67 as nanoalum with similar size characteristics but stabilized with a PEGylated
68 phospholipid did not produce TH1 responses. The nanoparticle form is also critical to
69 the activity of nanoalum, and Alhydrogel or PAA alone, or the combination of the two
70 but not in nanoparticle form, was incapable of inducing the same TH1 immune
71 response as our formulated nanoalum. We hypothesize that due to its presence at the
72 nanoparticle surface and thus direct interface with the immune environment, the
73 structure and composition of the PAA polymer has a direct impact on immune
74 response. To test this hypothesis, we evaluated the effects of polymer concentration,
75 molecular weight, formulation pH, and adsorption to Alhydrogel on the TH1 response
76 in mice immunized with the recombinant tuberculosis antigen ID93¹⁷. We also sought
77 to determine whether the induction of TH1 response by nanoalum was unique to
78 Alhydrogel as a starting material or if it can be reproduced with nanoparticles of a
79 different aluminum oxide phase. Through systematic modification and characterization

80 of nanoalum properties we were able to identify physicochemical correlations with
81 adjuvant activity and identify an optimal composition that induces a potent TH1 immune
82 response in mice.

83 **Experimental**

84 **Reagents**

85 Poly(acrylic acid) polymers of molecular weights 2,000 Da (63% soln. in water), 5,000
86 Da (50% soln. in water) and 30,000 Da (30% soln. in water) were purchased from
87 Polysciences, Inc. Poly(acrylic acid) polymers of molecular weights 2,000 Da (50%
88 soln. in water), 100,000 Da (35% soln. in water) and 250,000 Da (35% soln. in water)
89 were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Alhydrogel 2% EP was purchased from Sergeant
90 Adjuvants. Aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) nanopowder (<50 nm particle size by TEM) was
91 purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

92 **Synthesis of Nanoalum formulations**

93 In a 250 ml beaker, PAA solution was mixed with 90 ml of 10 mg/ml Alhydrogel 2% EP.
94 The amount of PAA added was determined by the target PAA:Al mass ratio and
95 concentration of the PAA stock solution. The mixture was adjusted to the desired pH
96 using 10 M sodium hydroxide and Q.S. to a final volume of 100 ml using deionized
97 water. The mixture was homogenized using a high speed mixer (Silverson machines)
98 at 5,000 rpm for 5 minutes. To reduce size to the nanometer scale, the mixture was
99 passed 10 times through a M110P microfluidizer (Microfluidics Corp.) at 30,000 psi.
100 The M110P's sample coil was held at 4°C using a recirculating water bath. The
101 microfluidized nanoalum was collected and sterile filtered using a 200 nm
102 polyethersulfone (PES) membrane.

103 **Particle size**

104 Hydrodynamic diameter of nanoalum particles was measured using the dynamic light
105 scattering technique (DLS, Malvern Instruments). Nanoalums were diluted 10-fold with
106 deionized water in disposable polystyrene cuvettes and prepared in triplicates.
107 Measurement parameters were as follows: material RI = 1.59, dispersant RI (water) =
108 1.33, T = 25°C, viscosity (water) = 0.887 cP, measurement angle = 173° backscatter,
109 measurement position = 4.65 mm, attenuation set to automatic. Particle size and
110 distribution were reported as the z-average diameter and polydispersity index (PDI),
111 respectively, both calculated from the intensity-weighted distribution averaged from
112 three measurements.

113 **Aluminum concentration**

114 Nanoalum samples (5 μ l) were dissolved overnight in 100 μ l concentrated phosphoric
115 acid (85 wt. %) and subsequently diluted to 10 ml with deionized water. Blank solution
116 (0.85 wt. % phosphoric acid), standards (0.1-10 μ g/ml) and samples were analyzed
117 using inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES, Perkin
118 Elmer Optima 8300). Aluminum content was determined by measuring absorbance at
119 396.153 nm, 308.215 nm and 394.401 nm. Average aluminum concentration in
120 samples was interpolated from linear fit of standards.

121 **Adsorption isotherms**

122 PAA and Alhydrogel mixed at various mass ratios, ranging from 0.1 to 5 mg PAA/mg
123 Al, were prepared at room temperature. Mixtures were vortexed 30 seconds, incubated
124 overnight at room temperature to reach equilibrium, then centrifuged for 10 minutes at
125 10,000 rpm to pellet Alhydrogel particles. The supernatant was collected and analyzed
126 for PAA content using Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, performed using
127 the attenuated total reflectance technique (Vertex 70, Bruker). Peaks corresponding to
128 the carbonyl group (1712 cm^{-1}), asymmetric (1550 cm^{-1}) and symmetric (1407 cm^{-1})
129 vibrations of the carboxylate anion, and the methylene group (1455 cm^{-1}) in the PAA

130 backbone were integrated to calculate their respective area under the curve (AUC)
131 values. The amount of PAA adsorbed to Alhydrogel was determined by comparing AUC
132 values from unbound PAA in supernatant to the actual amount added. The latter was
133 obtained from FTIR spectra of equivalent PAA solutions without Alhydrogel.

134 **Powder X-ray diffraction**

135 Samples were lyophilized and a small amount was deposited onto a Si <100>
136 substrate. A Cu k-alpha ($\lambda = 1.54$ angstroms) x-ray microsource was used to produce
137 the x-ray beam, which was passed through a 1.0 mm collimator and air scatter shield.
138 The detector used was a Pilatus 3R 100K-A 2D detector. Samples were rotated during
139 measurement to get a statistically representative view of all possible orientations. Scan
140 conditions: $2\theta/\theta$, 45 seconds per frame, 5.5 degrees frame increment from 4
141 degrees to 98.5 degrees 2θ .

142 **Mice, immunizations and tissue harvesting**

143 Female wild-type (WT) C57BL/6 aged 6-10 weeks were purchased from the Jackson
144 Laboratory and maintained in Specific Pathogen Free conditions. All animal studies
145 were approved by the Infectious Disease Research Institute Institutional Animal Care
146 and Use Committee. The facility where animal studies were conducted is accredited by
147 the Association for Assessment and Accreditation of Laboratory Animal Care,
148 International and follows guidelines set forth by the Guide for the Care and Use of
149 Laboratory Animals, National Research Council, 2011. Mice were immunized twice,
150 three weeks apart via an intramuscular injection in the calf muscles of hind limb with
151 0.5 μg of ID93 recombinant protein¹⁸. Spleens were collected in RPMI 7 days after the
152 second immunization. Cells suspensions were obtained by manual disruption. Red
153 blood cells contained in spleens were lysed using the Red Blood Cell Lysis Buffer
154 (ThermoFisher). Total viable cells were counted (Guava Technologies, Millipore) and

155 plated at 2×10^6 cells/well in round-bottom 96-well plates for flow cytometry or 2×10^5
156 cells/well for cytokine secretion.

157 **Flow cytometry**

158 For intracellular cytokine staining, cells were stimulated for 2 hours with media (RPMI
159 1640 + 10% FCS) or ID93 (10 μ g/ml) at 37°C and subsequently incubated with Brefeldin
160 A for an additional 8 hours at 37°C. Cells were surface stained with CD4 (clone RM4-
161 5), CD8 (clone 53-6.7), B220 (clone RA3-6B2), CD11b (clone M1/70) and CD44 (clone
162 IM7) together with Fc receptor block (anti-CD16/32 antibody), followed by
163 permeabilization with Cytotfix/Cytoperm (BD Biosciences) and intracellular staining with
164 CD154 (clone MR1), TNF (clone MP6-XT22), IL-2 (clone JES6-5H4) and IFN- γ (clone
165 XMG1.2). Antibodies were from BD Biosciences, BioLegend, or eBiosciences. Cells
166 were gated as singlets > lymphocytes > CD4+ CD8- B220- CD11b- > CD44+ >
167 cytokine+.

168 **Serum endpoint titer ELISA**

169 Peripheral blood was collect and subsequent centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for 5 minutes
170 to isolate the serum. Serum titers against ID93 were then evaluated by antibody capture
171 ELISA. Briefly, Corning high bind 384 well plates (VWR International) were coated
172 overnight at 4°C with 2 μ g/ml ID93 in coating buffer (eBioscience). Then, plates were
173 blocked with 1% BSA-PBS and serum samples serially diluted. Detection antibodies
174 were anti-mouse IgG2c or Ig1 HRP (Southern Biotech). Plates were analyzed at 450nm
175 (ELx808, Bio-Tek Instruments Inc.) and endpoints were set as the minimum dilution at
176 which values were lesser or equal to an OD of 0.2.

177 **Results**

178 **PAA concentration and molecular weight affects physicochemical and adjuvant**
179 **properties of nanoalum**

180 An adsorption isotherm measured at pH 7 showed that the amount of 2 kDa PAA
181 bound to Alhydrogel saturated at around 0.8 mg PAA/mg Al (Figure 1a), suggesting
182 that only 27% of PAA in our first generation nanoalum¹⁶ – formulated with 3 mg
183 PAA/mg Al – is adsorbed to Alhydrogel. We hypothesized that the excess free PAA
184 was not needed to produce sub-100 nm particles, and that the amount of PAA in
185 nanoalum can subsequently be reduced. To test our hypothesis we microfluidized
186 Alhydrogel with varying amounts of PAA, generating a series of formulations from 0.1
187 to 4 mg PAA/mg Al. Note that free or unbound PAA was not removed from the
188 formulations. As shown in Figure 1b, the hydrodynamic diameter decreased sharply
189 from >3 μm to around 100 nm as the amount of PAA was increased from 0.1 mg
190 PAA/mg Al to 0.6 mg PAA/mg Al. Further addition of PAA resulted in a slight reduction
191 of particle size, which plateaued around 80 nm. The size distribution, indicated by the
192 polydispersity index (PDI), ranged from 0.12 to 0.2 for all sub-100 nm nanoalum
193 formulations. At 0.8 mg PAA/mg Al the mean diameter of the adjuvant was not
194 significantly different than first generation nanoalum ($p = 0.18$, calculated using Mann-
195 Whitney test comparing multiple 0.8 mg/mg ($n = 7$) and 3 mg/mg ($n = 6$) nanoalum lots.
196 These data show that a minimum of 0.6 mg PAA/mg Al is needed to produce sub-100
197 nm nanoalum particles, which is 80% lower than the amount used in the first generation
198 nanoalum.

199 The molecular weight of a polymer can influence its structural conformation, which
200 can subsequently affect the polymer's interaction with dendritic cells¹⁹ and physiological
201 barriers²⁰. Due to its presence on the surface of Alhydrogel particles, we hypothesized
202 that the molecular weight of unbranched PAA will impact both nanoalum particle size
203 and adjuvant activity. We synthesized a series of nanoalum formulations with PAA
204 molecular weights ranging from 2 kDa to 250 kDa. Since the repeating carboxylic acid
205 groups in PAA engage and bind with the Alhydrogel particle surface, we normalized
206 PAA concentration by weight (3 mg PAA/mg Al) to ensure equimolar carboxylic acid

207 groups irrespective of PAA molecular weight. As observed in Figure 1c, the average
208 particle size increased with molecular weight, nearing 200 nm for the high molecular
209 weight polymers. We excluded nanoalums synthesized with 100 and 250 kDa PAA from
210 further evaluation due to considerable difficulty in sterile filtration. Adsorption isotherms
211 for 2, 5 and 30 kDa PAA nanoalums at pH 7 are shown in Figure 1a. PAA adsorption
212 to alum was proportional to PAA concentration and increased in a nonlinear manner,
213 asymptotically approaching a saturation limit that decreased with increasing molecular
214 weight.

215 Next, we sought to determine whether reducing the amount of PAA in nanoalum to
216 0.8 mg/mg Al – the saturation level of PAA adsorption to Alhydrogel – or altering the
217 PAA molecular weight relative to the first generation nanoalum would affect its TH1
218 adjuvant activity. We measured induction of functional CD4 cell populations in C57BL/6
219 mice immunized with the recombinant tuberculosis antigen ID93. The antigen stock
220 solution (1 mg/ml) was formulated in 10 mM tris buffer at pH = 7.4. An antigen dose of
221 0.5 µg and nanoalum dose of 100 µg Al was used for both prime and boost
222 immunizations. Mice (n = 5/group) were boosted on day 21 post-prime and euthanized
223 on day 28 to harvest spleens. As previously reported by us, compared to antigen alone
224 immunization, the first generation PAA nanoalum adjuvant (the latter identified with the
225 ‘#’ symbol in Figure 2) augmented the antigen specific CD4+ T cell response as
226 determined by expression of CD154, IFN-γ, TNF, and/or IL-2 upon antigen stimulation.
227 Reducing the amount of free PAA in the formulation did not significantly alter the
228 magnitude or quality of the response, whereas increasing the PAA MW from 2 to 5 kDa
229 somewhat increased the magnitude of the response. This trend reversed with a further
230 increase to 30 kDa PAA stabilized nanoalum. These data suggest that an optimized
231 nanoalum likely consists of 5 kDa PAA, and at a concentration of 0.8 mg PAA/mg Al.

232 **PAA adsorption to Alhydrogel and nanoalum adjuvanticity depend on**
233 **formulation pH**

234 The effect of pH on carboxylic acid ionization and adsorption to various metal oxides
235 is well documented²¹⁻²⁴. We postulated that since pH affects the ionization of carboxylic
236 acid groups²¹, it may affect adsorption of the polymer to Alhydrogel and consequently
237 impact adjuvant activity, therefore we synthesized a series of nanoalums identical in
238 PAA content compared to our predicted optimized nanoalum – 5 kDa PAA and 0.8 mg
239 PAA/mg Al – but formulated at different pH values ranging 4.7 to 9.0 prior to
240 microfluidization. Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy analysis of PAA in
241 nanoalum formulations (Figure 3a) showed an increase in carboxylic acid ionization
242 with increasing pH, as confirmed by the decrease in absorbance corresponding to
243 carbonyl (C=O) vibration at $\nu = 1712 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the complementary increase in
244 absorbance corresponding to the asymmetric ($\nu_{as} = 1556 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and symmetric ($\nu_s =$
245 1407 cm^{-1}) vibrations of the carboxylate anion. Furthermore, we measured an
246 approximately 8% reduction in PAA adsorption to Alhydrogel as pH increased from 3.0
247 to 6.0 (Figure 3b), followed by a substantial reduction (~36%) with another \log_{10}
248 increase to pH 7.0. The sharp inflection in adsorption coincided with the pKa of 5 kDa
249 PAA, which was measured as pH = 5.4 (Figure 3c). Interestingly the decrease in
250 adsorption as a function of pH did not translate to an inability to generate nanoalum
251 particles, as particle size of nanoalums was relatively independent of pH, averaging 83
252 nm with a RSD = 12% at pH values between 4.5 and 9.0. Next we assessed the effect
253 of pH on antigen binding with nanoalum (Figure 3d). ID93 alone or admixed with
254 nanoalums (5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ Al) was ultracentrifuged and the supernatant was analyzed for
255 protein content by gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE). Appearance of the 93 kDa protein
256 band in the supernatant and its low intensity relative to the ID93 alone control indicated
257 that the antigen was only partially bound to the PAA nanoalum; furthermore, formulation
258 pH did not seem to have a differential effect on ID93 adsorption to PAA nanoalum. Note
259 that the addition of 5 μg ID93 (pI = 5.03) per mg aluminum did not affect formulation
260 pH.

261 The CD4+ T cell response in mice (Figure 4a) decreased as pH increased from 5.6
262 to 7.0, mirroring the profile of the PAA adsorption isotherm. Similar to the cellular
263 response, there was no significant difference in the humoral response between pH 4.7
264 and 5.6 nanoalum groups but a significant reduction in IgG2c titers as pH increased to
265 7.0 and 7.6 (Figure 4b). Taken together, the immunogenicity data suggests that
266 nanoalum with pH 5.6 or lower produces the most potent TH1 cellular and humoral
267 responses. The accompanying physicochemical characterization suggests that
268 carboxylic acid groups in PAA are mostly protonated at pH 5.6 or lower and adsorption
269 to Alhydrogel is relatively high.

270 **CD4+ T cell differentiation depends on nanoalum core chemistry**

271 To determine whether the individually tailored nanoalum properties discussed above
272 (PAA amount, molecular weight and pH) produce an optimized nanoalum adjuvant
273 when combined in a single formulation, we synthesized a nanoalum using the 5 kDa
274 PAA at 0.8 mg PAA/mg Al and pH 5.5, and compared its adjuvanticity against the
275 prototype nanoalum (2 kDa PAA at 3 mg PAA/mg Al and pH 7.0) reported previously
276 ¹⁶. Secondly, we sought to determine the significance of the nanoparticle core crystal
277 structure and assess whether an aluminum oxide phase different from the AlO(OH)
278 structure of Alhydrogel affects nanoalum physicochemical characteristics and
279 adjuvanticity. A PAA-stabilized nanoalum composed of γ -Al₂O₃ phase (PAA-AO) – an
280 intermediate phase of aluminum oxide encountered during the phase progression from
281 boehmite (γ -AlO(OH)) to corundum (α -Al₂O₃)²⁵ – was synthesized under identical
282 processing conditions and composition as the predicted optimized nanoalum. The
283 intensity-weighted average hydrodynamic diameter of PAA-AO was 121 nm (PDI =
284 0.14), which was about 33% bigger than the Alhydrogel-based nanoalum formulations.
285 Like the Alhydrogel-based nanoalum, PAA-AO nanoalum formed stable nanoparticles,
286 maintaining its average particle size for up to a year at all storage temperatures (2-8°C,
287 25°C and 40°C). Powder x-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses (Figure 5a) revealed the

288 difference in aluminum oxide phase between the commercially available Alhydrogel
289 (AH) and γ -Al₂O₃ (AO) cores. The low diffraction intensity from the (020) plane (2-theta
290 = 14 degrees) relative to the reference pattern for boehmite (PDF# 00-021-1307)
291 suggested AH cores are composed of pseudoboehmite, which is a poorly crystalline
292 and nanofibrous version of boehmite (γ -AlO(OH))²⁶. The pseudoboehmite phase was
293 preserved in both prototype (PAA-AH proto.) and optimized (PAA-AH opt.) nanoalums,
294 except the (020) diffraction in the latter was significantly more intense than both AH
295 precursor and prototype nanoalum. The greater intensity indicates an increase in
296 number of (020) oriented crystals in optimized PAA-AH. The XRD pattern from the AO
297 precursor agreed well with the reference pattern for γ -Al₂O₃ (PDF# 04-007-2615) with
298 no notable change in the PAA-AO nanoalum. Next we measured adsorption of 5 kDa
299 PAA at pH 5.5 to the two aluminum oxide phases. As shown in Figure 5b, PAA
300 adsorption to the aluminum oxide nanoparticles was phase dependent, adsorbing
301 strongly to the pseudoboehmite phase of Alhydrogel but negligibly to γ -Al₂O₃. Finally,
302 comparing the ability to induce multifunctional CD4⁺ T cells in mice, the optimized PAA-
303 AH adjuvant was significantly more potent than the prototype PAA-AH and PAA-AO
304 nanoalums (Figure 5c). All nanoalum groups induced a balanced IgG2c/IgG1 response
305 confirming their ability to elicit a TH1-biased immune response compared to antigen
306 alone (Figure 5d).

307 **Optimized nanoalum is a potent inducer of TH1 immune responses in mice**

308 Previous studies have reported the adjuvant properties of PAA alone²⁷⁻²⁹, however
309 the molecular weights studied have typically ranged from 400,000 to several million
310 Daltons. We have found that low molecular weight PAA (2000 Da) alone does not
311 induce any adaptive immune response, but when strongly associated with Alhydrogel
312 particles and administered in a nanoparticle structure we observe a TH1 immune
313 response¹⁶. However there is no known clear threshold of PAA MW necessary for
314 adjuvant activity of the polymer alone, therefore we compared the optimized PAA-AH

315 nanoalum against Alhydrogel and 5 kDa PAA only controls (Figure 6). The robust
316 cellular and humoral responses show that the adjuvant activity is unique to the
317 nanoalum composition and not elicited with either Alhydrogel or the 5 kDa PAA
318 polymer. The antibody data also confirms that Alhydrogel induces a primarily TH2
319 response, indicated by the strong IgG1 response, and nanoalum induces a TH1 or
320 balanced IgG2c and IgG1 response. Both subclasses of IgG titers in the polymer only
321 group were not significantly different from the unadjuvanted group.

322 **Discussion**

323 Alum adjuvants, which are comprised of various aluminum salts such as aluminum
324 oxyhydroxide (AlO(OH)) and aluminum hydroxyphosphate (Al(OH)_x(PO₄)_y), primarily
325 induce a TH2 or humoral immune response against vaccine antigens that do not
326 possess intrinsic innate immune stimulating properties. The lack of a TH1 or cell
327 mediated response makes alum adjuvants relatively ineffective in eliciting protection
328 against intracellular infections such as tuberculosis and HIV. While the mechanisms of
329 action for alum adjuvants are manifold ³⁰, particle size and antigen adsorption are key
330 biophysical characteristics that govern stimulation and maturation of antigen presenting
331 cells (APCs). Structurally, Alhydrogel (AlO(OH)) consists of fibrous semi-crystalline
332 pseudoboehmite nanoparticles, each averaging about 4 × 2 × 10 nm in size ³⁰, but the
333 high surface area-to-volume ratio leads to their aggregation, forming 10-100
334 micrometer particles. We recently published on a high pressure microfluidization
335 process to physically disaggregate Alhydrogel nanoparticles and maintain it at a
336 nanoscale size using the anionic polymer polyacrylic acid (PAA) ¹⁶. The resulting
337 nanoparticle formulation – referred to as nanoalum – is a stable colloid with an average
338 particle size below 100 nm, physically resistant to multiple freeze-thaw cycles, and
339 induces multifunctional TH1 differentiation of CD4⁺ T cells in mice immunized with
340 either a recombinant tuberculosis or flu antigen. This improved adjuvant activity

341 resulted in an increase in protective efficacy against a lethal flu challenge compared to
342 micron-sized Alhydrogel.

343 The results presented in this study demonstrate that PAA adsorption to Alhydrogel
344 particles is a critical property that affects the adjuvant activity of nanoalum. In mouse
345 immunogenicity studies nanoalum-induced TH1 differentiation of CD4+ T cells and
346 serum IgG2c titers mirrored the adsorption curve suggesting a direct correlation
347 between adsorption strength and the quality and magnitude of the adaptive immune
348 response. PAA is known to electrostatically adsorb to metal oxides in a pH-dependent
349 manner^{22, 23}. We found that adsorption to Alhydrogel is also pH-dependent and in
350 general decreases with increase in pH. The rise in pH causes carboxylic acid
351 deprotonation and conversion to carboxylate anions, leading to electrostatic repulsion
352 between anions that cause the polymer chain to linearize and prefer dissolution over
353 adsorption²². Previous studies have shown that the surface of AlO(OH) is also affected,
354 as increasing pH causes deprotonation of surface -OH₂⁺ groups³¹, thus reducing the
355 surface cationic charge. We postulated that with increasing pH, the simultaneous
356 reduction in the cationic character of Alhydrogel and increase in anionic character of
357 PAA diminished electrostatic association, resulting in the observed reduction in PAA
358 adsorption to AlO(OH) particles. Interestingly the decrease in adsorption did not
359 translate to an inability to generate stable nanoalum particles but did correlate with a
360 reduction in TH1 response, suggesting that PAA adsorption to Alhydrogel is potentially
361 critical to the adjuvant's mechanism for inducing CD4+ T cells. Although not elucidated
362 in this paper, a possible mechanism of action is nanoparticle drainage to lymph nodes
363 and subsequent activation of resident APCs. Targeting particulate adjuvants and
364 antigens directly to lymph nodes is shown to promote a TH1 type immune response,
365 indicated by an increase in serum IgG2 titers and IFN- γ production from re-stimulated
366 splenocytes^{32, 33}, similar to responses observed in this study. Other studies have

367 suggested that nanoparticles effectively draining to lymph nodes co-stimulate APCs
368 with antigen can drive maturation and subsequent priming of lymphocytes^{34, 35}.

369 Finally, we evaluated the effect of the nanoparticle core on nanoalum activity and
370 report that induction of multifunctional CD4+ T cells depends on the aluminum oxide
371 phase of the nanoalum core. Unlike Alhydrogel, nanoalum derived from γ -Al₂O₃
372 nanoparticles was unable to induce CD4+ T cells in mice. Williams et al. have shown
373 that the layered double hydroxide (LDH) of AlO(OH) is a critical chemical determinant
374 of its adjuvant activity³⁶. Interestingly, powder XRD analysis suggest that compared to
375 Alhydrogel or the prototype nanoalum, the optimized PAA-stabilized Alhydrogel
376 nanoalum contained a greater number of crystals oriented in the [020] direction, which
377 corresponds to the LDH structure²⁶. It is yet unclear whether enhanced TH1 induction
378 by the optimized nanoalum adjuvant is due to a higher fraction of LDH structure in the
379 nanoparticle core and we are further investigating this relationship.

380 **Conclusions**

381 Nanoalum is a stable nanoparticle formulation of the clinically approved adjuvant
382 Alhydrogel, developed using a scalable top-down manufacturing process. Previous
383 studies exploring adjuvant properties of aluminum salt-based nanoparticles have
384 utilized in-house synthesized nanoparticles and primarily focused on adaptive humoral
385 immune responses. Our approach was to reprogram a commercially available and
386 clinically relevant alum adjuvant and screen physicochemical properties that induce
387 both humoral and cellular immune responses. Unlike Alhydrogel, which induces
388 primarily a humoral immune response, its stable nanoparticle form (nanoalum) induces
389 both humoral and cellular immune responses characterized by TH1-cytokine secreting
390 CD4+ T cells. Our results suggest that induction of the TH1 response correlates with
391 adsorption of the polyacrylic acid stabilizing polymer to Alhydrogel and also depends
392 on the phase of the aluminum oxide. Collectively, these data highlight tunable

393 properties of nanoparticle adjuvants stabilized with surface adsorbed polymers in order
394 to affect immunological response. Further exploration of structurally similar
395 nanoparticle-polymer systems offers a promising approach to develop nanomaterials
396 with engineered biological activity. This new class of adjuvant may have particular
397 benefit in the immunization of at risk-populations such as newborns and pregnant
398 women for whom aluminum-based adjuvants are well accepted but traditional micron-
399 sized alum adjuvants do not promote the optimal immune response needed to provide
400 protection.

401

402 **Conflicts of interest**

403 APK, CBF and MTO are co-inventors on a patent application (US201662344347P)
404 describing the nanoalum adjuvant.

405 **Author Contributions**

406 Conceptualization: APK, SGR, DC, CBF, MTO; Data Curation: APK, HL, ACS, MTO;
407 Formal Analysis: APK, HL, CBF, MTO; Methodology: APK, HL, ACS, MTO; Writing –
408 original draft: APK; Writing – review and editing: APK, DC, CBF, MTO; Funding
409 acquisition: DC, MTO; Supervision: SGR, DC, CBF, MTO.

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413 R43IP001109-01-00. The table of contents graphic was created with Biorender.com.

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493 Figure 1: (a) Effect of PAA concentration and molecular weight on adsorption to Alhydrogel.

494 Hydrodynamic size of nanoalums as a function of (b) 2 kDa PAA concentration and (c) PAA

495 molecular weight at 3 mg PAA/mg Al

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499 Figure 2: Effect of varying PAA composition on multifunctional CD4+ T cell responses. Mice
 500 were immunized with the recombinant tuberculosis antigen ID93 alone or adjuvanted with
 501 nanoalum consisting one of the specified PAA compositions. First generation nanoalum is
 502 labeled with the # symbol. Data in each stack presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD).
 503 For statistical analysis, CD4+ T cells from each animal (N = 5) were aggregated and
 504 compared using ordinary one-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple comparisons test. **P<0.01

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507 Figure 3: (a) FTIR spectra of nanoalums stabilized with PAA at pH values 9.0 (A), 7.6 (B),
 508 7.0 (C), 5.6 (D) and 4.7 (E). Inset highlights the decrease in carbonyl (C=O) vibration at 1712
 509 cm⁻¹ with increasing pH. Spectra F and G are reference spectra of 5 kDa PAA at pH 3.0 and
 510 8.2, respectively. Spectrum H is reference spectrum of Alhydrogel. (b) PAA adsorption to
 511 Alhydrogel as a function of pH and at a fixed PAA:Al mass ratio of 0.8 mg/mg. Data points
 512 represent mean \pm SD of triplicate measurements. (c) Titration curve of 5 kDa PAA polymer
 513 with 10M sodium hydroxide. pKa of 5.4 indicated with dotted line. (d) SDS-PAGE analysis of
 514 supernatant collected from ID93 admixed with 5 kDa PAA nanoalum formulated at various
 515 pH values. Lane 1= pH 4.6, lane 2 = pH 5.6, lane 3 = ladder, lane 4 = pH 5.8, lane 5 = pH
 516 7.0, lane 6 = pH 7.5, and lane 7 = ID93 without nanoalum.

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520 Figure 4: Effect of nanoalum pH on immunological responses in C57BL/6 mice. Mice
 521 immunized with ID93 were adjuvanted with 5 kDa PAA nanoalum formulated at one of the
 522 indicated pH values. (a) Multifunctional CD4⁺ T cells isolated from splenocytes and (b)
 523 serum anti-ID93 IgG endpoint titers on day 28 post-prime. Data presented as mean \pm SD. For
 524 statistical analysis of CD4⁺ T cell data, cytokine responses from each animal (N = 5) were
 525 aggregated and analyzed using ordinary one-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple comparisons
 526 test. Antibody data in (b) was log₁₀ transformed and analyzed using two-way ANOVA and
 527 Tukey's multiple comparisons. *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ****P<0.0001

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531 Figure 5: (a) Powder x-ray diffraction patterns of Alhydrogel (AH), prototype PAA-stabilized
 532 AH (PAA-AH proto.), optimized PAA-stabilized AH (PAA-AH opt.), γ -Al₂O₃ (AO) and PAA-
 533 stabilized AO (PAA-AO). Reference patterns for Boehmite (PDF# 00-021-1307) and γ -Al₂O₃
 534 (PDF# 04-007-2615) with relative peak intensities are shown as vertical lines. (b) Adsorption
 535 isotherms showing binding of 5 kDa PAA (pH = 5.5) with Alhydrogel AH or AO particles. (c)
 536 Immunogenicity data showing multifunctional CD4⁺ T cells isolated from splenocytes and (d)
 537 serum endpoint IgG2 and IgG1 titers on day 28 post-prime (7 days post-boost). C57BL/6
 538 mice were immunized with the recombinant tuberculosis antigen ID93 alone or adjuvanted
 539 with a nanoalum adjuvant. Data in (b) and (c) presented as mean \pm SD. For statistical
 540 analysis of CD4⁺ T cell data, cytokine responses from each animal (N = 5) were aggregated
 541 and analyzed using ordinary one-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple comparisons test.
 542 Antibody data was log₁₀ transformed and analyzed using two-way ANOVA and Tukey's
 543 multiple comparisons test. *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.0005, ****p<0.0001

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547 Figure 6: Immunogenicity of lead nanoalum adjuvant compared to Alhydrogel, 5 kDa PAA
 548 and unadjuvanted groups. Female C57BL/6 mice were immunized with the recombinant TB
 549 antigen ID93. (a) Multifunctional CD4⁺ T cells in mouse spleens. (b) Serum anti-ID93 IgG
 550 endpoint titers on day 28 post-prime. Data shown as mean ±SD. For statistical analysis of
 551 CD4⁺ T cell data, cytokine responses from each animal (N = 5) were aggregated and
 552 analyzed using ordinary one-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple comparisons test. Antibody
 553 data in (b) was log₁₀ transformed and analyzed using two-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple
 554 comparisons. *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.001, ****P<0.0001

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TOC figure

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